

Open innovation and crowdsourcing research: A bibliometric mapping and cluster analysis using VOSviewer and Biblioshiny

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This paper reveals the developments of open innovation and crowdsourcing research in business and management through bibliometric literature analysis. The authors collected documents from Scopus and analyzed the data using Biblioshiny, RStudio package for descriptive analysis, and VOSviewer for science mapping. Useful insights resulted in the most cited contributions in open innovation and crowdsourcing research by different authors, research articles, and journals through cluster analysis. This study adds value to open innovation and crowdsourcing research by analyzing the bibliometric data during 2013–2022. Future studies may consider collaboration and increased footprint across emerging markets such as Africa, India and South America.

Keywords: open Innovation, bibliometric analysis, crowdsourcing

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Introduction

Open innovation has grown exponentially as a concept of interest in scholarly research and managerial practice across the globe. Studies in open innovation have provided an increased understanding of how firms capitalize on external knowledge creation to foster innovation (Dahlander & Gann 2010, Randhawa et al. 2016). A particular mechanism of open innovation is crowdsourcing, which has since emerged as a prominent, innovative practice. Howe (2006) originally defined crowdsourcing as taking a task performed traditionally by a designated employee or a contractor and outsourcing it by making an open call to an undefined yet significant group of people. By engaging in crowdsourcing, firms search outside their boundaries for successful problem-solving (Chesbrough & Bogers 2014, Ghezzi et al. 2018). The firm discloses the details of the problem and invites anyone deemed qualified to solve the problem (Afuah & Tucci 2012, Jeppesen & Lakhani 2010). The term "open innovation" has appeared in many publications and has influenced research beyond open innovation. The impact on practice can be seen in the industry adoption of the term, with middle managers adopting "open innovation" in their job titles and industry press releases touting the latest "open innovation" initiatives. In terms of research, there has been a greater focus on the inbound mode of open innovation, and an epistemic community has formed around the term, with researchers increasingly identifying as "open innovation" researchers. Clubs of firms interested in open innovation have formed worldwide, providing a place for industrial managers to share experiences and practices. Governments have also taken up open innovation at all levels. Overall, the development of open

innovation has become increasingly institutionalized, challenging traditional views of innovation management and bringing about a range of literature reviews.

The paper is structured as follows: First, a literature review is provided, detailing the developments of open innovation in terms of the level of analysis, the types of organizations, and data sources. Second, the methodology describes the steps in conducting the systematic bibliometric analysis, followed by the results and discussion of the findings. The paper has conclusion and implications of the study.

Literature Review: Developments in Open Innovation

This section reviews developments in open innovation in terms of its level of analysis, the types of organizations and industries investigated, and the methods used for these lines of inquiry. In open innovation literature, scholars have identified five levels of analyses: individual, firm, inter-organizational, extra-organizational, and regional and societal (Bogers et al. 2017). Most research has focused on the firm level, examining how external sources of innovation are incorporated into the organizational design, practices, and processes (Foss et al. 2013). Some studies have explored open innovation in the context of SMEs, entrepreneurs, and new entrants (Zobel et al. 2016). Additionally, the inter-organizational and extra-organizational levels have gained attention in recent years, investigating the role of external stakeholders in knowledge creation and innovation, including user innovation, communities, consortia, and collaboration within broader networks or ecosystems (West & Boger 2014). Notably, other levels of analysis have received inadequate attention, creating a need for a multi-level understanding of open innovation. Bogers et al. (2017) found that exploring individual, psychological, regional, and societal levels could provide a comprehensive understanding of the open innovation paradigm, as limited research at these levels continues to hinder the holistic experience of open innovation.

Open innovation has expanded beyond multi-national companies since the start of open innovation research by Chesbrough (2003) toward small and medium-sized firms (Brunswick & van de Vrande 2014). Eftekhari and Bogers (2015) studied the application of open innovation in start-ups, while others have explored open innovation applications in manufacturing, marketing, services, tourism, national regions, and public policy (Bogers et al. 2018, Egger et al. 2016). Although the profit-driven principles of open innovation are defined by Chesbrough & Bogers (2014), researchers have only recently considered the application of open innovation in government agencies and independent not-for-profit organizations.

Open innovation and crowdsourcing research have primarily been undertaken through quantitative surveys. Qualitative research mainly employed a single or multiple case study approach through two distinct data collection methods: interviews with participants and extensive content analyses of the crowdsourcing platforms. Few studies have conducted longitudinal research in open innovation and crowdsourcing. Studies in open innovation and crowdsourcing have only conducted systematic and bibliometric reviews until 2013 (Randhawa et al. 2016). This study looks at the developments of open innovation and crowdsourcing research since 2013. Previous studies should have considered the intellectual contributions, keywords used, most productive journals, annual average production co-occurrence of keywords, and network mapping from the past ten years. The current article attempts to fill the literature gap through a systematic literature review using bibliometric analysis techniques to complement the existing literature studies. To discover what lies beneath the developments in open innovation and crowdsourcing research in the past ten years, our objectives are to find (1) most cited authors (2) most cited articles (3) most cited journals and (4) most frequently used keywords.

The main objective of this study is to systematically review open innovation and crowdsourcing research to evaluate the overall past developments, collaborations, interventions, and different aspects of open innovation, to provide a conclusive remark. To attain this objective, bibliometric analysis is proposed to review the past studies systematically. The bibliometric analysis method, science mapping, was used for this paper, which is a useful method that examines how disciplines, fields, specialties, and individual

papers are related to one another. It produces a visual-spatial representation of the findings that help understand the nature of the literature and aids in identifying potential gaps in the literature for future research.

Methodology

Bibliometric analysis is a key measure for evaluating scientific production (Singh & Basha, 2023). The bibliographic data is produced by scientists working in the field who express their opinions through citations, collaboration, and writing. It systematically analyzes published bibliographic literature (Donthu et al. 2021). Bibliometric analyses are used for reasons such as evaluating the performance of journals or authors, analyzing and mapping a specific scientific field, and informing and identifying potential research areas in the literature.

Data Extraction

The bibliometric data has been collected from the Scopus database to provide more significant insights and development in open innovation and crowdsourcing research. Systematic searching and filtering of data were conducted. Authors searched the database with specific search keywords, refined the search criteria, considered appropriate studies, and analyzed the data. These three steps are further detailed below. The data was first extracted using the following search syntax: TITLE ("open innovation" OR "crowdsourcing"). A total of 10536 documents were extracted. Search criteria were redefined to include the relevant studies. The authors narrowed down the years of publication to only the past ten years. As highlighted in the literature discussion, this study is a bibliometric review following the work of Randhawa et al. (2016), who conducted a bibliometric analysis of open innovation research during 2003–2012. The data was limited to only include subject areas related to business and management sciences, only final research articles in journals, and written in English. The search syntax for the refined search was as follows: TITLE ("open innovation" OR "crowdsourcing") AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE, "final")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "BUSI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "English" OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "j")) AND (LIMIT-TO(PUBYEAR, 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2013)). Ultimately, 1321 articles were extracted for further bibliometric analysis.

Results and Discussion

The consideration period of 2013–2022 and the total number of documents extracted for bibliometric analysis were 1321. The average year from publication is 3.96; the average citations per year are 3.46; the average citations per document are 28.1. There are 2920 authors; out of them, 113 are single-authored articles. The average co-authorship per document is 3.05. Two relevant aspects were considered when evaluating an author's relevance within a specific field, productivity and impact. Both measures overview the top ten critical contributors of open innovation and crowdsourcing research between 2013 and 2022. The productivity was evaluated through the number of articles published by an author in the given period, while impact was assessed by considering the number of citations received each year. Through a cluster analysis, 1179 authors met the threshold of a minimum of five articles and a minimum of 30 citations. The number of citations on an author's works signifies the quality of the research and relevance within the field of study. As represented in Table 1, the authors with the maximum impact are Bogers M, Vanhavebeke W, Chesbrough C, Brunswicker S, and Majchrzak A, each with more than 1100 citations since 2013. The total link strength indicates the total strength of the citation links of a given author with other authors. The top authors also have relatively high total link strengths, indicating that they engage and collaborative research practices with the authors within the bibliometric dataset.

Table 1. Top 10 Contributing Authors in Open Innovation and Crowdsourcing

Rank	Author	Citations	Articles	Total link strength
1	Bogers M	1773	11	158
2	Vanhaverbeke W	1497	12	210
3	Chesbrough H	1449	16	108
4	Brunswick S	1146	5	114
5	Majchrzak A	1110	8	83
6	Grimaldi M	653	14	188
7	Meissner D	559	9	35
8	Santoro G	555	5	33
9	Cheng CCJ	547	7	61
10	Cricelli I	539	11	148

Source: the authors

The cluster analysis was conducted to determine the key contributing research articles. A minimum threshold of 30 citations per research article was considered. Of the 74383 cited references, 113 met the threshold. Through a cluster analysis, the VOSviewer output divides the total research article citations into five Clusters having 113 items, 4547 links, and a total link strength of 17946. The most cited reference is Dahlander and Ghann (2010) in Cluster 1 (red-colored cluster) followed by Laursen and Salter (2006) and Gassmann et al. (2010) in Cluster 2 (Green-coloured cluster). Specific sub-topics in the area of open innovation and crowdsourcing influence the characteristics of each cluster. Upon further cluster analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Cluster Map of Most Cited References from Research Articles

Source: the authors

The authors identified that the most cited research articles grouped into Cluster 1 related to empirical studies focused on measuring open innovation (e.g., Scuotto et al. 2017). Cluster 2 contained cited articles

on topics related to Open Innovation reviews (Van de Vrande et al. 2010, West et al. 2014), cluster 3 represented conceptual papers from the earlier years of Open Innovation (Chesbrough 2003, Elmquist et al. 2009, Laursen & Salter 2006). Cluster 4 represented papers focusing on crowdsourcing, crowd sciences, and innovation contests (Afuah & Tucci 2012, Howe 2006, Terwiesch & Xu 2008).

The journal citations were analyzed to determine the key contributing journals in open innovation and crowdsourcing research. A journal's citation indicates that it has been referred by the scholars in their studies and cited for being the most relevant paper in that area. The threshold chosen for the VOSviewer output was a minimum number of five articles per Journal and 20 citations per Journal. Figure 2 shows that Technological Forecasting and Social Change had the highest citations (2714) among the sources with an impact factor of 10.88; Research Policy had the second highest citations (2039), and the Journal of product innovation management the third highest citation (1573). In the VOSviewer output, the dot size specifies the number of citations for a particular journal. The line represents the links between journals.

Figure 2 Cluster Map of Most Cited Journals

Source: the authors

In order to determine the most occurring keywords given by authors in open innovation and crowdsourcing research, a minimum threshold of ten occurrences of keywords was considered. Of the 3335 author keywords, 45 met the keyword cluster analysis threshold. VOSviewer output for keyword co-occurrence divided the keywords into seven clusters with 298 links and a total link strength of 1055. Cluster 1 (red-colored) had 11 keywords: crowdsourcing, co-creation, motivation, creativity, gamification, and idea generation. Cluster 2 (green-colored cluster) had 11 keywords containing absorptive capacity, innovation performance, human capital, and intellectual capital. Cluster 3 (dark-blue-colored cluster) has seven items and includes keywords such as SMEs, technology transfer, knowledge transfer, and Small to medium enterprises. Cluster 4 (purple-colored cluster) and Cluster 5 (yellow-colored cluster) contained six items each. With only three keywords, Cluster 6 (light-blue-colored) has entrepreneurship, strategy, and collaboration. Cluster 7 (orange-colored cluster) concluded with a single keyword: value creation. Table 2 summarizes the keyword occurrences.

Table 2. Top 20 Keyword Occurrences during 2013-2022

Rank	Keywords	Occurrences	Total link strength
1	Open innovation	692	562
2	Crowdsourcing	246	169
3	Innovation	94	139
4	SMES	58	87
5	Collaboration	34	69
6	Absorptive capacity	33	53
7	Inbound open innovation	31	39
8	Innovation performance	31	52
9	Case study	28	55
10	New product development	25	49
11	Innovation management	24	43
12	Knowledge management	23	39
13	Entrepreneurship	23	20
14	Social media	22	34
15	Firm performance	22	37
16	Outbound open innovation	21	27
17	Performance	20	29
18	Trust	18	37
19	Creativity	17	28
20	R&D	17	34

Source: the authors

Conclusion

The purpose of this research paper was to provide an understanding of potential gaps in open innovation and crowdsourcing research by determining its key contributors by evaluating the most cited authors, research articles, journals, and keywords, and thus determining new areas for future research.

Open innovation and crowdsourcing research have attracted increasing attention from authors, but the seminal authors Bogers M, Vanhabeke W and Chesbrough C remain the most cited. The high link strengths indicate increased collaborative research practices among the authors within the bibliometric dataset. Through cluster analysis, the key contributing research articles and journals remain those of seminal authors in open innovation and crowdsourcing research. Two of the top three most cited research articles provide a detailed literature and bibliometric review of open innovation research. These papers have formed the foundation for this study, as their years were limited from 2003 to 2013 and 2014. Regarding the most popular author keywords, open innovation, crowdsourcing, innovation, SMEs, and absorptive capacity were found across most bibliometric data.

The study assists business management scholars and practitioners interested in pursuing open innovation and crowdsourcing research within their contexts. It represents a comprehensive bibliometric overview of the scientific literature produced in the past ten years. Scholars can leverage the results of this study to address future studies. One main conclusion is that most open innovation and crowdsourcing research is conducted and affiliated with developed countries. Further collaboration remains high amongst European countries, North American countries, and Australia. The study reveals a geographical knowledge gap in open innovation and crowdsourcing research. The limited availability of open innovation literature in Africa, South America, and the Pacific may restrict opportunities for collaboration globally. Therefore, future studies should consider collaborative open innovation and crowdsourcing research across emerging markets such as Africa, South America, and India. Open innovation can drive

innovation, economic growth, and social development. The lack of academic literature on open innovation in Africa may delay the development of robust innovation ecosystems, hindering the collaboration between academia, industry, and other stakeholders necessary for fostering innovation in such emerging markets. The study has limitations. First, the dataset was collected through Scopus to obtain higher-quality results, limiting the number of analyzable publications. Exclusion criteria were imposed to improve the bibliometric analysis (i.e., publication year, document type, language, subject areas, etc.)

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